

An Analysis of the Role of Work Motivation and Work Discipline in Improving Employee Performance: Job Satisfaction as a Mediating Factor (Case study on PT Prima Sejati Sejahtera I)

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ABSTRACT: This study analyzes how worker motivation and discipline affect performance through job satisfaction. Using primary data, this study is quantitative. This study took a sample of all workers totaling 48 people because the population was below 100. Path analysis and multiple linear regression are used. The hypothesis of this study produces the following conclusions: work motivation, discipline, and job satisfaction improve employee performance at PT Prima Sejati Sejahtera I. Work motivation and discipline increase job satisfaction in employees. PT Prima Sejati Sejahtera I workers will be more productive when job satisfaction is high, because they can moderate the relationship between work motivation and work discipline.

KEYWORDS: Employee performance, Job satisfaction, Work motivation, Work discipline.

INTRODUCTION

The most valuable asset of any company is its employees. Usually, businesses usually follow a specific plan when they run their operations to maximize the efficiency and effectiveness of their employees. Without solid and trustworthy leadership, it is difficult for a business to manage its people. In order for every worker to feel personally involved in the company's intended goals, businesses develop maximum performance enablement plans. The company's goals will not be achieved without competent workers. To achieve their goals, the organization's employees follow a system that consists of routine and repetitive tasks. To achieve these goals, a business needs high-quality material, financial, and human resources (Swastha, 2007).

A person's ability to perform a job depends on his skills, his work ethic, and his financial resources. The results of a job are influenced by a person's skills, level of commitment, and years of experience, as stated by Hasibuan (2010). The quantity and quality of employee output is a measure used to measure their performance in the workplace. Robbins (2003) argues that the motivation-skill relationship exists in employee performance. Veithzal (2005) states that employee performance is their total results over a certain period of time in a meeting that sets and agrees on criteria, goals, or benchmarks in work.

Basically, the factors that stimulate and trigger individuals to work at the highest level in the workplace are the same factors that drive them to achieve organizational goals. The concept of motivation is defined by Robbins & Judge (2006) as a mechanism that explains the dynamics of intensity, orientation, and perseverance when striving for a desired goal. Motivation is a commitment that may be offered to a person to enable them to carry out activities that are in line with their beliefs. Motivation can be demonstrated by the aspiration to put in more effort and achieve a higher level of achievement than previously experienced, as well as a strong commitment to achieving pre-set goals.

Work discipline is to enforce employee compliance with business policies. According to Handoko (2014), work discipline is a managerial task that ensures that various procedures are carried out in accordance with the standards set by the company. Furthermore, work discipline is described as employee awareness and compliance with all applicable company regulations (Hasibuan, 2008). An organizational structure that seeks to minimize errors, deviations, or omissions that cause waste in carrying out work must include work discipline because it is a key variable in the development of human resource management. Organizations may find it easier to achieve their goals with strong work discipline, according to Rivai (2017). Discipline in the workplace helps workers get their work done and stay on track, which in turn increases productivity and prevents mistakes that may be detrimental to the business. Achieving personal and professional success requires self-discipline.

An employee's job satisfaction level can be defined as the extent to which they derive personal satisfaction from their work in an organization. According to Robbins (2006), "job satisfaction is a positive feeling towards a job that is the result of an evaluation

of several characteristics". Luthans and Avolio (2009) define job satisfaction as an optimistic emotional state caused by employees' views of the value of the job and their personal experience of it. Pleasant attitudes and actions taken by a person towards his or her job while working in a company or organization are job satisfaction.

THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS

Work Motivation

The drive to achieve a goal is the driving force behind most actions. The Latin verb movere "to encourage, or cause an action or deed" is the origin of the United Kingdom term we know today. According to Robbins and Judge (2017), the ability, direction, and perseverance of efforts to achieve a specific goal can be explained through the process of motivation. A common source of motivation is the desire to achieve goals, with the primary focus on organizational goals. According to Hasibuan (2014), Maslow's theory of work motivation includes physical needs, security and safety needs, social needs, self-esteem needs, and self-activity.

Work Discipline

The desire of individuals who are aware to comply with organizational regulations in pursuit of these goals is what Handoko (2008) calls "work discipline", and Sedarmayanti (2018) argues that it is necessary to evaluate and sanction employees who comply with company policies. The company's management efforts to maintain the rules and regulations that must be complied with by all workers are known as work discipline (Subyantoro & Suwanto, 2020). Discipline in the workplace means following the official and informal policies of the organization (Sutrisno, 2009). Carelessness, injustice, or irregularities can lead to inefficiencies in the workplace, therefore work discipline is very important (Nurchahyo, 2011). Communication with workers in a way that motivates them to change behavior is the core of the work discipline, which aims to increase awareness and compliance with all relevant social norms and company requirements (Rivai, 2016).

Job Satisfaction

The term "job satisfaction" refers to the level of satisfaction or dissatisfaction of an individual with his or her job (Rivai & Sagala, 2011). Researchers have demonstrated that when a person is satisfied at work, it is beneficial to the individual, to the employer, and to society at large (Sutrisno, 2016). Gap theory, equity theory, and two-factor theory are the three most well-known approaches to understanding what factors contribute to employee job satisfaction levels (Bang, 2012).

Employee Performance

What is meant by employee performance according to Wibowo (2006) is a chain reaction of actions taken by workers that help or hinder the achievement of company goals. Employee performance is the final result of an organization's efforts or a management process, this can be proven through measurable and clear data (Sedarmayanti, 2018). According to different schools of thought, an employee's performance is the final result of his efforts in meeting the demands of his work (Bangun, 2012). Mangkunegara (2009) stated that performance is the sum of the qualitative and quantitative outputs of an employee as a consequence of fulfilling his job duties (Norianggono et al., 2014).

FRAMEWORK OF RESEARCH AND HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

Figure 1. Research Outline

The research that has been conducted by Jufrizen (2021), Putra & Fernos (2023) and Hakman et al. (2021) tried to find out how a strong drive to work affects how well employees complete the work charged to them. Studies have shown that employee motivation has a big influence on how well they do their jobs. To improve overall efficiency, it is important to keep workers motivated to do a better job. Motivating employees with motivation is an effective strategy to inspire them to work at the highest level and meet management expectations.

H1: Work motivation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance

Studies on this subject have been conducted by Hustia (2020) and Putra, Fernos (2023) and Audina & Handayani (2021). The purpose of the study is to ascertain and highlight the characteristics that lead to a well-organized work environment and increased productivity in the workplace through a disciplined attitude at work. The results show that discipline in the workplace improves employee performance and significantly changes the relationship between the two. The direct impact of work discipline on work productivity causes employee discipline to work as a crucial operational function of MSDM. Without strict rules and regulations, the business world and other institutions will find it difficult to work optimally. Munandar (2008) stated that performance evaluation is the process of evaluating employee (or manager) character attributes, work activities, and results to improve work performance and inform decision-making. behavior in the world of work.

H2: Work discipline has a positive and significant effect on employee performance

Individual satisfaction at work affects employee performance is explored by Amalia & Makduani (2022) and Nurhandayani (2022). This study found that satisfaction in a person's job has a significant effect on the output produced, in this case employee performance. How satisfied a person is with their work will be the determining factor in the final achievement of their performance. Employee satisfaction levels will vary according to their respective value systems. A person's performance is defined by Hasibuan (2006) as the extent to which he uses knowledge, ability, honesty, and time to achieve goals.

H3: Job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on employee performance

A study conducted by Rivaldo & Ratnasari (2020) and Rasyid & Tanjung (2020) found that when companies provide incentives to their employees, it can increase their happiness at work. The level of job satisfaction will be directly correlated with the quality of the incentives given to employees. Based on the findings of this study, there is a strong correlation between employee motivation and satisfaction. The study found that intrinsic motivation has a positive effect on professional growth, which in turn increases job satisfaction.

H4: Work motivation has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction

Nandita & Rosdiana (2023) and Yuliantini & Santoso (2020) are among the researchers who found a strong correlation between self-control at work and happiness at work. When workers are happy or dissatisfied with their jobs, this is due to several factors, including the company's leadership style, the quality of the relationship between colleagues and managers, the overall work environment, and the overall business climate.

H5: Work discipline has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction

To improve employee performance, which in turn helps the company achieve its goals and make workers happy, top-level management must observe the behavior and actions of workers. Achieving superior performance is not easy because it depends on the ability of the organization or company to control and accept the elements that affect it, such as worker motivation, competence, success, and job satisfaction. Garaika' s research (2020) shows that job satisfaction plays a mediator in the relationship between work motivation and performance. However, this study shows that job satisfaction can affect the impact of intrinsic motivation on performance. This shows that the level of internal motivation experienced in the workplace has a direct impact on the level of individual job satisfaction.

H6: Work motivation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance through job satisfaction

Employees have the ability to easily adapt to various work rules and standards, resulting in exemplary behavior due to strong work discipline, according to research by Pratama and Dihan (2017). What makes a worker happy, enjoy, or hate his job depends on his or her interaction with the work environment, his mental attitude, and his own performance evaluation. This is what we mean when we talk about job satisfaction. Employee performance is determined as the final result of their efforts in completing the tasks

given (Sandy, 2015). This research was conducted with the aim of understanding the relationship between work discipline, job satisfaction, motivation, and performance. The findings of this study show that work discipline exerts a great influence on employee performance, while job satisfaction serves as a mediator in this relationship.

H7: Work discipline has a positive and significant effect on employee performance through job satisfaction

RESEARCH METHODS

This study examines the influence of motivation and work discipline on employee performance by using job satisfaction as an intermediate variable. Using primary data, this study is quantitative. A total of 48 employees from PT Prima Sejati Sejahtera I Sewing Section in Line 32 participated as participants, so the samples taken used census techniques. Data were collected using questionnaires. Path analysis, multiple linear regression models 1 and 2 to determine the strength of a variable.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Validity Test

As long as the value of the correlation coefficient of each question is greater than the r value (0.361), then the questions about work motivation, work discipline, work discipline, and employee performance are correct and can be used as a measuring tool. Table 1 shows that there is data that has been valid for hypothesis testing.

Table 1. Validity Test Results

No	Variabel	r calculate	r table
1	Work Motivation	0,730	0,361
		0,723	
		0,585	
		0,759	
		0,812	
2	Work Discipline	0,785	0.361
		0,688	
		0,810	
		0,820	
		0,834	
3	Job Satisfaction	0,778	0.361
		0,742	
		0,806	
		0,698	
		0,763	
4	Employee Performance	0,621	0.361
		0,814	
		0,768	
		0,689	
		0,774	

Source: 2024 primary data, processed

Reliability Test

Alfa Cronbach is a way to know if the data you have is accurate or not. Reliability is indicated by a ± greater than 0.60. The reliability test in table 2 shows that all variables are reliable, which means that all questionnaire questions can be used to find out something.

Table 2. Reliability Test Results

No	Variabel	Alpha
1	Work Motivation	0,762
2	Work Discipline	0,845
3	Job Satisfaction	0,812
4	Employee Performance	0,781

Source: 2024 primary data, processed

Path Analysis Test

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis Model 1

Job satisfaction (Z), discipline (X2), and intrinsic motivation (X1) all affect employee performance (Y). With an R-squared value of 0.805 in SPSS 25, we can see that intrinsic factors such as job satisfaction, discipline, and motivation account for 80.5% of the variance of worker output. Employee performance is influenced by work motivation, discipline, and job satisfaction as shown by the F test with a significance value of 0.000. The results of the work motivation t-test of 2.499 with a significant of 0.01 showed that the sig value in the variable was less than 0.05, indicating that there was a statistically significant influence between work motivation and employee performance. Work discipline had a significant effect on employee performance (p=0.02). An effect of work discipline on employee performance is indicated by the significance threshold value of 0.02 which is less than 0.05. Job satisfaction has a significant effect on employee performance with a sig value of 0.02, the sig value in this job satisfaction variable is lower than 0.05. The regression equation of model 1 based on table 3 is as follows

$$Y = a + 0,311 \text{ Job Motivation} + 0,315 \text{ Work Discipline} + 0,328 \text{ Job Satisfaction} + e2$$

Based on the findings of the research on the results of the multiple linear regression analysis in table 3, it can be concluded that each independent variable is proven to have a positive and significant influence on employee performance. It is likely that one or all of these independent variables will result in an improvement in employee performance, and vice versa.

Table 3. Results of Multiple Linear Regression Analysis Model 1

Model		Standardized Coefficients	t hitung	Sig.
		Beta		
1	(Constant)		-0,196	0,846
	Work motivation	0,311	2,499	0,016
	Work Discipline	0,315	2,286	0,027
	Job Satisfaction	0,328	2,364	0,023

Source: 2024 primary data, processed

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis Model 2

This equation tests how work motivation and discipline in work affect job satisfaction. Work drive and discipline explained 76.9% job satisfaction according to SPSS 25 with an R Square value of 0.769. Job satisfaction is influenced by motivation and work discipline, according to the F test (0.000). With a significance level of 0.00, work motivation has little effect on job satisfaction. Because of the relevance value of 0.00, work discipline has an impact on job satisfaction. The results of the t-test of work motivation of 2.955 with a significant of 0.00 showed that the value of the sig in the variable was less than 0.05, indicating that there was a statistically significant influence between work motivation and job satisfaction. Work discipline has a significant effect on employee performance with a calculated t-value of 4.550 with a significant of 0.00, the result of this significance value is lower than 0.05. The regression equation of model 2 based on table 4 is as follows

$$Y = a + 0,362 \text{ Work Motivation} + 0,557 \text{ Work Discipline} + e2$$

Based on the findings of the research on the results of the multiple linear regression analysis in table 4, it can be concluded that each independent variable is proven to have a positive and significant influence on employee performance. If one or all of these independent variables are taken into account, there will be a tendency to increase job satisfaction as well, and vice versa.

Table 4. Results of Multiple Linear Regression Analysis Model 2

Model		Standardized Coefficients	t hitung	Sig.
		Beta		
1	(Constant)		1,471	0,148
	Work motivation	0,362	2,955	0,005
	Work Discipline	0,557	4,550	0,000

Source: 2024 primary data, processed

Sobel Test

Work motivation has a calculated t-value of 1.798, exceeding the table's t-value of 1.677 at a significance level of 0.05 determined by the Sobel test. Work motivation and performance are influenced by job satisfaction. Work motivation and performance are influenced by job satisfaction. Work discipline had a tcount of 2.066 higher than the ttable of 1.677 in the sobel test. Job satisfaction affects work discipline and performance. Job satisfaction moderates the effects of work discipline performance.

Table 6. Sobel Test Results

Variabel	Sobel test statistic	One-tailed probability
Work Motivation	1,798	0,03
Work Discipline	2,066	0,01

Source: 2024 primary data, processed

DISCUSSION

Both the p-value and the t-value are below the level of significance shown by statistical analysis. So, the hypothesis that there is a strong correlation between work discipline and productivity is true. If we want to improve the performance of our employees, we need to find ways to inspire them to do a better job. If you want your staff to give everything and meet management standards, you have to encourage them. Motivating employees results in better performance, according to previous research conducted by Jufrizen (2021), Putra & Fernos (2023), Hakman et al. (2021) and Audina & Handayani (2021).

Both the p-value and the t-value are below the level of significance shown by statistical analysis. This provides more support for claims that self-control in the workplace significantly increases output. Institutions such as businesses and government agencies will find it difficult to function efficiently if there are no strict rules and regulations. According to Munandar (2008), appraisal is about paying attention to personal qualities, job responsibilities, and the results of managers or employees to increase productivity and guide decision-making. The findings of this study corroborate the findings of Putra & Fernos (2023) and Hustia (2020), two other studies that also found that work discipline has a significant impact on productivity.

Both the p-value and the t-value are below the level of significance shown by statistical analysis. This lends credence to the idea that employee satisfaction levels in the workplace greatly affect their output. Different workers will have different levels of satisfaction based on their personal value system. Hasibuan (2006) states that an individual's performance can be described as the extent to which he utilizes knowledge, talent, honesty, and time to achieve goals. The findings of this study corroborate the findings of Amalia & Makduani (2022) and Nurhandayani (2022) who also found that worker satisfaction in the workplace has a significant impact on their productivity.

A p-value of 0.005 is less than a significance level of 0.05, according to calculations. In addition, the important t-value is 1.677, and the calculated t-value is 2.955, which is higher. Therefore, the relationship between intrinsic motivation in the workplace and in the workplace is statistically significant, as expected. When incentives are of low quality, workers' satisfaction with their work will decrease. A strong correlation between intrinsic motivation and job satisfaction was found in this study. Supporting other studies that show that job satisfaction has a significant effect on employee performance, the findings of this study add weight to the research of Rivaldo & Ratnasari (2020) and Rasyid & Tanjung (2020).

Statistical analysis yielded a t-value of 4.550 and a significance level of 0.000, which was below the threshold of 0.05. Therefore, the theory that there is a strong correlation between work discipline and job satisfaction is correct. Several factors play a

role in determining whether or not employees are satisfied with their jobs. These include the organization's management style, the nature of the relationship between employees and supervisors, the physical workplace, and the economic situation. Finding that job satisfaction has a significant and crucial effect on performance, the findings of this study corroborate the findings of Nandita & Rosdiana (2023) and Yuliantini & Santoso (2020).

Both the p-value and the t-value are below the level of significance shown by statistical analysis. As a result, the hypothesis states that job satisfaction is the main pathway where intrinsic motivation in the workplace affects productivity. Executives must keep an eye on staff activities and behaviors to improve performance, which is beneficial to the company's bottom line and employee morale. Managing and accepting the factors that affect performance including employee motivation, competence, success, and job satisfaction is a challenge for any organization or business that wants to achieve exceptional results. According to Garaika (2020) research, job satisfaction modulates the relationship between intrinsic motivation and output quality. However, the results of this study imply that intrinsic motivation may have an influence on performance, and job satisfaction may moderate this effect. This shows that a person's level of job satisfaction is influenced by their intrinsic motivation at work.

Statistical examination shows a p-value below 0.05 and a t-value below the threshold of 2.066 with 1.677 as the threshold. Therefore, it is true that job satisfaction plays an important role in the relationship between work discipline and employee performance. According to research conducted by Pratama and Dihan (2017), workers can freely regulate their behavior in accordance with applicable laws and regulations and high work standards. Factors that affect the level of job satisfaction of an employee include his mental attitude, his interaction with his work environment, and his own assessment of his own performance. When we talk about satisfaction with our work, this is what we mean. The essence of an employee's efforts in completing his or her work that day is a review of his performance (Sandy, 2015). The purpose of this study is to better understand the relationship between work discipline, job satisfaction, motivation, and performance. The results of this study show that job satisfaction mediates the relationship between work discipline and employee performance.

CONCLUSION

The conclusion drawn from the discussion of the hypothesis is that the performance of employees of PT Prima Sejati Sejahtera I Sewing Section Line 32 is positively and significantly influenced by work motivation, work discipline, and job satisfaction. Employees of Line 32 of the Sewing Section of PT Prima Sejati Sejahtera I reported higher levels of job satisfaction when they were motivated and disciplined at work. Workers at PT Prima Sejati Sejahtera I Sewing Section Line 32 will be more productive when they report high levels of job satisfaction, which in turn moderates the relationship between motivation and disciplinary actions used in the workplace.

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